

Lecturer Self-Awareness Index: measuring the alignment between lecturer and student perception

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Abstract

During last decades, there was a transformation in the Engineering Education field that resulted in the widespread use of Active Learning techniques, with the goal to place the student at the center of the learning process. However, there was a lack of effective ways to evaluate how a course uses those techniques. Although Active Learning has already been validated as an effective way to influence student learning and is increasingly being validated into the classroom, there was no way to qualify and evaluate the use of Active Learning techniques by faculty members, until the proposal of a conceptual model, called Engineering Education Active Learning Maturity Model (E²ALM²). The application of E²ALM² uses questionnaires applied to course lecturers and their students. This article proposes the Lecturer Self-Awareness Index (LSAI), that derives from E²ALM², as a complement to measure the discrepancy between lecturer and student perception. LSAI allows a lecturer to identify items in which his perception diverges from students'. This tool can help improve decisions in course preparation and lead to a better delivery.

Keywords: Active Learning; Engineering Education; assessment; self-awareness

1 Introduction

One of the great challenges of higher education in the 21st century is to adapt traditional teaching techniques to the reality of today's students, who have different characteristics from previous generations (Hartikainen, Rintala, Pylväs, & Nokelainen, 2019). Student-centered strategies increase student engagement, which is linked to teaching effectiveness. The positive results have already been widely explored (Burke & Fedorek, 2017; Cho, Mazze, Dika, & Gehrig, 2015; Prince, 2004).

Engineering Schools eager to modernize educational practices need to understand their current maturity of Active Learning, which can be the first step of a renovation program. To achieve this goal, Arruda & Silva (2021) present the Engineering Education Active Learning Maturity Model (E²ALM²). This framework processes data collected from students and lecturers of a course to depict the current maturity level of the Active Learning implementation in terms of five dimensions, composed of 14 key success factors (KSF) that summarize 41 constructs.

Self-awareness is positively associated with transformational leadership (Titrek & Çelik, 2011), leadership performance and success (Axelrod, 2012; Caldwell & Hayes, 2016; Showry & Manasa, 2014; Whetten & Cameron, 2016). It leads to better decision making, once it connects the past and present experience (Kamenov, 2013), and supports effective learning, because the more students know their 'self', the better they increase their own personal developments (Murphy, 2007). Furthermore, self-awareness increases sympathy (Boyer, 2010; Gair, 2011; Smith, 2011), reduces egocentrism (Gendolla & Wicklund, 2009; Scaffidi Abbate, Boca, & Gendolla, 2016), and is perceived as central to improving management skills (Whetten & Cameron, 2016).

Regardless of the specific maturity level in active learning implementation, the perceptions of students and lecturers can be quite misaligned, due to the natural difference in points of view. The aim of the Lecturer Self-Awareness Index (LSAI) is to depict these possible discrepancies and provide the decision-making process with feedback between how lecturers and students perceive the benefits and characteristics of a given active learning implementation.

In this article, the concept of self-awareness is emphasized, bringing some definitions, motivations, and limitations. Additionally, the concept of Active Learning is presented, followed by E²ALM² details. Then, LSAI is

defined and detailed. Finally, we conclude with some discussions about the advantages and limitations of the index.

2 Self-awareness

Although the term self-awareness is widely used in practitioner and scientific publications, the exact meaning of the term is still unclear (Carden, Jones, & Passmore, 2022). The literature brings several definitions of self-awareness (Nutt Williams, 2008; Sutton, 2016; Sutton, Williams, & Allinson, 2015), but confusion between the concepts of self-awareness, self-knowledge and self-consciousness is common (Morin, 2017; Sutton, 2016). Also, definitions seem to depend on focus and context (Sutton, 2016).

Goleman (1995) defines self-awareness as “knowing one’s internal states, preferences, resources, and intuitions”. There are statements that self-awareness refers to the constant consciousness of feelings, thoughts and behaviors (Harrington & Loffredo, 2010; Nutt Williams & Fauth, 2005) and how someone’s behaviors impact other individuals (Mayer, Salovey, & Caruso, 2004).

In their systematic literature review, Carden et al (2022) offer the following definition:

“Self-awareness consists of a range of components, which can be developed through focus, evaluation and feedback, and provides an individual with an awareness of their internal state (emotions, cognitions, physiological responses), that drives their behaviors (beliefs, values and motivations) and an awareness of how this impacts and influences others.”

However, self-awareness is a difficult journey. Practicing it may feel risky and frightening for some students, and its development requires a safe learning environment (Feize & Faver, 2019). In the process of developing self-awareness, a person might find discrepancies between the real self and the ideal self (Gallwey, 2001; Silvia & Duval, 2001).

Finally, Govern and Marsch (2001) discuss the manipulation and measurement of levels of situational self-focus. Titrek (2011) analyses the Self-Awareness Competence Scale and Demerouti et al (2011) state that a high level of self-awareness could be considered as a high consistency between self-evaluation and the evaluations of others.

3 Active Learning and its assessment

Despite the vast literature available on Active Learning, there is still no consensus definition on the topic. Hartikainen (2019) shows 66 definitions grouped by three main categories: (1) defined and viewed as an instructional approach; (2) not defined but viewed as an instructional approach; and (3) not defined but viewed as a learning approach. We highlight three popular definitions: “any instructional method [used in the classroom] that engages students in the learning process” (Prince, 2004), “an umbrella term for pedagogies focusing on student activity and student engagement in the learning process” (Roehl, Reddy, & Shannon, 2013) and “an umbrella term that now refers to several models of instruction, including cooperative and collaborative learning, discovery learning, experiential learning, problem-based learning, and inquiry-based learning” (Barkley, 2010).

In the Engineering Education field, it is possible to identify several movements with the objective of modernizing programs and teaching process, such as the CDIO initiative (Crawley, Malmqvist, Östlund, Brodeur, & Edström, 2014), the change in ABET's accreditation criteria (called EC2000) (Lattuca, Terenzini, & Volkwein, 2006), and the greenfield creation of engineering colleges with proposals totally different from the traditional 20th Century model, such as Olin College (Goldberg & Somerville, 2014) and Aalborg University (Mohd-yusof, Arsat, Borhan, Graaff, & Kolmos, 2013).

A common point among the modernization movements in the engineering education field is the recommendation to place the student at the center of the learning process, which drives the increasing use of active learning techniques (Hartikainen et al., 2019).

From the consensus on the importance of using Active Learning techniques, there are different levels of maturity in this subject. At one extreme, it is possible to observe isolated actions of teachers who experience a change in a course. At the other extreme, there are programs designed as project-based, with materials and assessment methods aligned, in addition to adequate infrastructure for classes in formats different from the traditional model, in which students attend the class in rows watching a lecturer in front of the classroom.

Considering the growing popularity of these techniques, Arruda & Silva (2021) introduce the Engineering Education Active Learning Maturity Model (E²ALM²), a framework that allows practitioners to assess the current maturity level of Active Learning implementation in a course. This framework can support diagnosis and practical improvements in real settings.

3.1 E²ALM² method

The Engineering Education Active Learning Maturity Model (E²ALM²) (Arruda & Silva (2021) was built from a literature review of key success factors (KSF) for Active Learning implementations, which were divided into five dimensions: content quality, organizational environment, organizational infrastructure, lecturer and interactions. These five dimensions are subdivided in fourteen KSF. Each KSF is composed of one or more constructs, adding up to 41 constructs in total. Each construct is detailed in variables, totaling 89 of them.

At the lowest level, each variable has a grade. To apply the model to real cases, two questionnaires are used: Student Questionnaire (SQ) and Lecturer Questionnaire (LQ). Figure 1 shows the E²ALM² structure and those questionnaires.

Figure 1 - E²ALM² structure and questionnaires

Each question in the questionnaires is linked to a variable, and based on the result obtained in this question, a value is assigned (Question value). Figure 2 shows the condition to calculate this value. From the Question Value of all questions, the score for the linked variable is calculated. The construct score is the average of the variables that compose it. The KSF score is the average of the constructs that compose it. Due to its nature, there are variables that are present in both questionnaires and others that are present in only one of them.

Figure 2 - Question value condition

Then, to calculate the dimension score, the grades of the KSF that compose it and the weights are used, calculated from the application of the Analytical Hierarchy Process – AHP method (Saaty, 2008), with answers from paired comparisons of importance between the KSFs that make up the evaluated dimension. These answers were provided by Active Learning experts consulted specifically for this purpose. Figure 3 shows the process to calculate the dimension score.

Figure 3 - Dimension score process

4 LSAI Method

As the application of the E²ALM² is based on the responses of the students and the lecturer, it is possible that there are divergences between the perceptions of both sides. Due to this fact, the Lecturer Self-Awareness Index (LSAI) was created as a way of identifying the discrepancy between the two points of view. Figure 4 shows the E²ALM² framework and its KSFs that make up the LSAI.

Figure 4 - E²ALM² framework and LSAI components

Due to its nature, LSAI can only be calculated from KSF that have both student and lecturer measurements. It is calculated from the difference of each question in the Student Questionnaire and in the Lecturer Questionnaire. The maximum value (5) indicates that the lecturer's perception is fully aligned with the students' perception, while the minimum value (0) indicates the total misalignment between the two perceptions.

4.1 LSAI composition

The constructs that compose the LSAI calculation (those that have scores in both the SQ and the LQ) are shown in the Table 1.

Table 1 - LSAI constructs and Key Success Factors

Construct	Key Success Factor	Dimension
Use of real-life problems	Course Activities	Content Quality
Application of active experiments	Course Activities	Content Quality
Variety of instructional resources	Course Activities	Content Quality
Adequacy to Learning Outcomes (LO)	Course Activities	Content Quality
Clearness of assessment methods	Student Assessment	Content Quality
Clearness of criteria for success	Student Assessment	Content Quality
Communications with students	Student Assessment	Content Quality
Preparation of students to conduct activities required	Learning Facilitation	Content Quality
Classrooms designed for improve active learning experience	Classrooms	Organizational infrastructure
Classrooms equipped with technologies to enhance student learning and support teaching innovation	Classrooms	Organizational infrastructure
Availability of technology	Technology	Organizational infrastructure
Accessibility of technology	Technology	Organizational infrastructure
Usability of technology	Technology	Organizational infrastructure
Interactions students/lecturers	Interactions with lecturers	Interactions

As shown in the table 1, LSAI is calculated from just six KSF: Course Activities, Student Assessment, Learning Facilitation, Classrooms, Technology e Interactions with lecturers.

According to Arruda & Silva (2021), those KSF have following specifications:

- Course Activities (problems, projects or cases studied) should: engage students with real-life problems and active experiences; provide students with a variety of additional instructional resources, such as simulations, case studies, videos, and demonstrations; be suitable to achieve different targets including the support of the students' learning process and establishing learning outcomes requirements; be clearly written, in the right length, useful, flexible, and provide appropriate degree of breadth; have suitable intellectual challenge; and begin with an explanation of its purpose.
- Student Assessment needs to be clear, concise, and consistent. This involves instructions, assignments, assessments, due dates, course pages, and office hours. Furthermore, criteria for success must be communicated clearly and monitored.
- Learning facilitation includes the preparation of students to conduct activities and tasks required in addition to activities related to the facilitator guiding the learning process of the students. It also involves providing students with regular opportunities for formative feedback from the lecturer.
- Classrooms should be designed for improve Active Learning experience and be equipped with technologies that can enhance student learning and support teaching innovation.
- Technology involves availability, reliability, accessibility, usability of devices, internet (Wi-Fi), learning support, and inclusive learning environment.
- Interaction between students and lecturer supports knowledge construction, motivation, and the establishment of a social relationship. Furthermore, constructive, and enriching feedbacks from the lecturer lead to increasing academic success and feelings of support.

As can be seen in the specifications above, in addition to the nature of the LSAI, all the KSFs that make up this indicator have the potential for different perceptions by the lecturer and the students. However, the capacity to trigger actions to improve the course (and the conditions that surround it) is much more concentrated on

the lecturer than on the students, because although the lecturer acts as a facilitator and co-constructor of learning, he has a role in the organization structure. This way, it is possible to identify students as clients of the service provided by the organization and it is essential that there is a way to assess how much the lecturer's perception is in fact aligned with the perception of clients (students) in relation to this service.

5 Discussion

The application of E²ALM² allows the diagnosis of a course in the five dimensions that make up the index, as already discussed. As a way of representing the result, a radar chart is constructed, as in figure 5.

Figure 5 - Example of E²ALM² real application

For each KSF, lecturer and student perceptions may converge or diverge. Possible combinations are shown in figure 6.

Figure 6 - Student and lecturer perceptions

From the answers to the questionnaires, the LSAI in your six KSF is also calculated. The line LSAI = 0 is the bisector of the quadrant shown in the figure 7. Analyzing the example shown as follows, it is possible to identify that the KSF in which perceptions are most discrepant is "Classrooms".

Figure 7 - LSAI results

In this example, KSF “Classrooms” is a component of the dimension “Organizational infrastructure”, which had the lowest grade between five dimensions of E²ALM². Then, while this dimension is possibly a course weakness, the lecturer’s and students’ perception are misaligned. This way, any effective improvement action could be hampered.

Looking at this example, two variables of KSF “Classrooms” are shown: (i) % of activities performed in an environment suitable for Active Learning and (ii) % of activities performed in a technologically appropriate environment. So, if the lecturer is not concerned with finding more suitable physical spaces for the activities of the course, this indicator will hardly improve. Thus, students’ perception of quality will remain compromised. Here, it is important to remember that self-awareness as considered as central to improving management skills (Whetten & Cameron, 2016).

As a limitation, it is important to highlight that E²ALM² does not assess the quality of a course but identifies the maturity level related to active learning. In addition, data collection made only with questionnaires can lead to bias or have answers that reflect some student dissatisfaction with other factors. Finally, it is essential to highlight the importance of validation of the questionnaires, to eliminate another kind of bias. This validation is still planned to future steps.

6 Conclusion

Active Learning is a broad concept that has been boosted during last years, especially in the Engineering Education field. As a first step to an improvement plan, it is necessary to diagnose the status of a course. Then, to assess the maturity level of an AL implementation, E²ALM² is used.

Additionally, self-awareness is understood as an important capacity to high levels of leadership, better decision making and management skills. Thus, this concept is intrinsically linked to the path to improvement actions, with the goal of upgrading course conditions and evaluation.

After E²ALM² application, some factors can show misalignment between lecturer’s and students’ perceptions. To identify this discrepancy, this paper presented Lecturer Self-Awareness Index (LSAI). This index supports the identification process of critical factors that need special attention to get better results to students.

As future work, we suggest a quantitative study, comparing different applications of E²ALM². This study is ongoing and will be the subject of future work. Initially, it was focused on five courses, from Brazil and Portugal. These cases are being studied and will serve to better understand both the application process and the search for cause-effect relationships between practices and results, in addition to serving as a basis for the validation of questionnaires, the main information collection tool. This could be a start of a predictive model, that can provide hints and suggest approaches to enrich courses.

7 References

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